

Table 1. Grain and rice equivalent yields as sole crop and intercrop. Varanasi, India, 1985-86.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)							
	Rice		Intercrop		Rice equivalent		Net return (US\$)	
	1985	1986	1985	1986	1985	1986	1985	1986
Sole rice in 30-cm rows	2.20	1.60	—	—	2.20	1.60	153.45	63.15
Sole rice in paired rows (20+40 cm)	2.20	1.50	—	—	2.20	1.50	149.92	57.35
Sole pigeonpea in 60-cm rows	—	—	0.77	0.69	1.70	1.60	128.60	104.41
Sole black gram in 30-cm rows	—	—	0.91	0.75	1.80	1.50	135.00	87.94
Sole sesame in 30-cm rows	—	—	0.56	0.47	1.70	1.50	141.69	99.26
Rice + pigeonpea (1:1) in 30-cm rows	1.00	0.70	0.44	0.38	2.01	1.57	123.89	58.89
Rice + black gram (1:1) in 30-cm rows	1.30	0.87	0.55	0.43	2.40	1.73	201.32	103.45
Rice + sesame (1:1) in 30-cm rows	0.74	0.53	0.36	0.26	1.88	1.33	136.17	57.64
Paired rows rice + pigeonpea (2:1)	1.66	1.04	0.24	0.19	2.22	1.50	112.27	8.75
Paired rows rice + black gram (2:1)	2.10	1.48	0.41	0.38	2.92	2.24	228.75	132.42
Paired rows rice + sesame (2:1)	0.92	0.63	0.32	0.23	1.93	1.37	97.86	10.29
LSD (0.05)	0.095	0.065	—	—	0.127	0.095	14.85	13.30

The red loam soils offer the possibility of companion pulses or oil seed crops, to stabilize and increase production. We tested an intercrop combination during 1985-86.

The soil of the experimental field had 0.3% organic C, 0.035% total N, 64 kg available P, and 201 kg available K. Crop varieties used were Akashi for rice, T21 pigeonpea, T9 black gram, and T13 sesame. The experiment was laid out in

randomized block design.

Rice grain yield differed significantly with intercropping pattern in both years (Table 1). Rice alone in rows 30 cm apart produced maximum grain yield of 2.2 t/ha the first year and 1.6 t/ha the second year. Rice + sesame gave the lowest rice yield. Rice + black gram (2:1) gave the same rice yield as rice alone, in both 30 cm rows and paired rows.

Table 2. Land equivalent ratio (LER) of intercropping. Varanasi, India, 1985-86.

Treatment	LEK ^a	
	1985	1986
Rice + pigeonpea (1:1) in 30-cm rows	1.05	1.01
Rice + black gram (1:1) in 30-cm rows	1.21	1.14
Rice + sesame (1:1) in 30-cm rows	0.99	0.88
Paired rows of rice + pigeonpea (2:1)	1.09	0.96
Paired rows of rice + black gram (2:1)	1.41	1.46
Paired rows of rice + sesame (2:1)	0.99	0.90
LSD (0.05)	0.06	0.07

^aLER = sum of the yields of each intercrop a) a fraction of its monoculture check.

Rice + black gram 2:1 had the highest net return (\$229 and \$132/ha). Highest land equivalent ratio (LER) was also with rice + black gram 2:1, followed by rice + black gram 1:1; the lowest LER was with rice + sesame (Table 2). Rice exhibited the highest competitive ability with pigeonpea and the lowest with sesame. □

Effect of green manure and inorganic N in rice - rice - pulse cropping system

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We studied the effect of green manure and inorganic N on total yield of a rice - rice - pulse cropping system in the field 1987-88. The study was laid out with green manure in the main plot and inorganic N in the subplots, in a split-plot design with three replications.

Soil was clay loam (Alfisol) with pH 8.3, CEC 26 meq/100 g soil, and 248-24780 kg available NPK/ha.

Crotalaria juncea raised in a separate field was cut 45 d after sowing, chopped and buried at 12.5 t/ha, 1 wk before transplanting rice (IR50 in the dry season, IR60 in the wet season). N was

Effect of organic and inorganic N on rice - rice pulse yields. Treatments identified with the same letter within a green manure treatment are not significantly different by Duncan's Multiple Range Test.

applied at 0, 100, 150, and 200 kg/ha in four equal splits: basal, at tillering, panicle initiation, and heading. K was split-applied with N at 42 kg/ha. P was

basal at 22 kg/ha. Green gram Co 3 was raised without manure after wet season rice.

Green manure significantly increased

rice yields in both seasons: + 1.0 t/ha in the dry season, + 0.5 t/ha in the wet season (see figure). Rice yields increased with increased N. Highest yield in the

dry season was with 200 kg N/ha; and with 100 kg N/ha in the wet season. Green gram yields did not vary

significantly with residual green manure or applied N at rates above 100 kg N/ha. □

Residual effect of fertilizer applied to rice in rice - fallow - cotton

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In Cauvery delta of south India, rice - rice - cotton and rice - cotton are common crop rotations. We evaluated the effect of fertilizer applied to the second season rice crop on rice - fallow - cotton during 1987 and 1988.

Experiment field soil was Entic Chromustert with pH 7.4, CEC 30.8 meq/100 g, 0.75% organic C, 295-15-325 kg available NPK/ha and E.C. 0.2 dS/m.

The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design. Main plot treatments were rice with no fertilizer and 100 kg N, 22 kg P, and 42 kg K/ha individually and in combination. The subplots were

Residual effect of fertilizer applied to rice on cotton yields in a rice - fallow - cotton rotation. Aduthurai, India, 1987-88.

Fertilizer to rice (kg NPK/ha)	Yield (t/ha)							
	Fertilizers applied to cotton							
	First year			Mean	Second year			Mean
	0-0-0	60-13-25	30-6.5-12.5		0-0-0	60-13-25	30-6.5-12.5	
0-0-0	1.0	1.4	1.4	1.3	1.4	1.7	1.5	1.5
100-0-0	1.3	1.5	1.4	1.4	1.6	1.9	1.9	1.8
100-22-0	1.5	1.6	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.9	1.8	1.7
100-0-42	1.5	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.9	1.9	2.0	2.0
100-22-42	1.6	1.7	1.7	1.6	1.5	2.1	1.7	1.8
Mean	1.4	1.6	1.5		1.6	1.9	1.8	
LSD between 2 fertilizer treatments of rice at different levels of fertilizer to cotton				0.7				1.7
LSD between 2 fertilizer treatments of cotton at different levels of fertilizer to rice				1.0				2.4

rice - fallow - cotton (MCU7) with no fertilizer, 60-13-25 kg NPK/ha and 30-6.5-12.5 kg NPK/ha.

Half the fertilizer recommended for cotton was adequate, since the residual

effect of 100-0-42 kg NPK/ha applied to the preceding rice crop was pronounced (see table). The residual effect of P on cotton was negligible. □

Effect of source and level of nitrogen on yield of rice and succeeding lentil crop

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We studied the residual effect of urea and modified urea on yields of rice and a succeeding lentil crop grown without fertilizer 1986-87 and 1987-88.

The soil was sandy to clay loam with pH 8.1; 0.38% organic C, 10 kg available P/ha, 233 kg available K/ha. Wet season rice was followed by dry season lentil in a randomized block design with four replications.

N source had a significant residual effect on the succeeding lentil yield (see table). Urea supergranule (USG) deep placement in rice had the highest

Effect of source and level of N on grain yield of rice and the residual effect on lentil yield. Crop Research Station, Ghagharaghat, India, 1986-87 and 1987-88.

Treatment	Rice yield (t/ha)		Lentil yield (t/ha)	
	1986	1987	1986	1987
<i>Nitrogen sources</i>				
Prilled urea (1/2 basal + 1/2 topdressed after first flood receded)	2.0	1.7	1.2	1.1
Prilled urea (1/2 basal + 1/2 foliar spray after first flood receded)	2.0	1.6	1.2	1.0
Lac-coated urea (basal)	2.7	2.4	1.3	1.2
Neem-coated urea (basal)	2.8	2.6	1.4	1.3
Urea supergranules (placed 8-10 cm deep after first flood receded)	2.9	2.8	1.7	1.6
LSD (0.05)	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
<i>Nitrogen level (kg/ha)</i>				
0	1.1	1.1	0.9	0.8
30	2.7	2.5	1.3	1.2
60	2.9	2.7	1.5	1.4
LSD (0.05)	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.1

residual effect on lentil yield; neem-coated urea (basal) and USG did not differ statistically. Prilled urea in 2 splits had very low residual effect.

The increase in lentil yield after

modified urea applied to rice is explained by the significantly lower loss of N through leaching, denitrification, and ammoniacal volatilization. □